

Bhasi knows this as well. So, he turns to Mukundan to intervene on his behalf. Mukundan sets out to save Bhasi's home but is completely swayed by Power House Ramakrishnan. The latter knowing how recognition-hungry Mukundan is and how easily he would succumb to flattery uses that as his weapon to sweep over Mukundan's objections and has him actually agreeing to become a part of the community hall committee. Mukundan betrays Bhasi his friend and alienates Anjana, the woman he is in love with. [Anjana is still married to another man and would therefore be considered an unsuitable love by the community hall committee.] Mukundan however does not perceive it as betrayal and stubbornly clings to the belief that what he has done is right. But it takes the death of Achuthan Nair, his father to make him realize how empty his life was and would continue to be without either Bhasi or Anjana. He is stricken by both remorse and guilt. And the realization that he was no better than his father whom he had despised all his life. With this comes the real transformation. Mukundan decides to make amends. And how he goes about it is an indicator to how much Mukundan has changed. From a fastidious and colorless man lacking in courage to take even the slightest of risks, Mounding becomes a man capable of finding love and happiness. A man who discovers the varied vibrant hues of life. A man who emerges from the shadow of his father's personality to become a better man.

Kit Reed, writing in *The New York Times*, says "A genial, meandering tale filled with false alarms and diversions, *The Better Man* is slowed by loops in the story, by abandoned threads of plot. Charming as it is, the novel gathers momentum only at the end, when Bhasi and Mukundan find themselves at odds just in time for the drama of conflict and resolution." Another review in *The Hindu* said "Anita Nair's first book, *The Better Man*, was a finely structured novel set in a small Kerala village. Mukundan, her hero, returns to the village, hoping to exorcise bitter memories. Anita Nair not only has a wonderful knowledge of life in the village, but shows an almost Dostoevskian feeling for the undercurrents of consciousness, as Mukundan seeks and finds redemption."

The Literary Review column of *The Hindu* said "*The Better Man* had all the right ingredients according to the critics. Today, with her second book *Ladies Coupe*, one would imagine ANITA NAIR would have achieved the same results. Critics have opined otherwise..." As already stated Anita Nair is an Indian best-selling author of Indian poetry with her famous novels, "*The Better Man*" and "*Ladies Coupé*". Born in Kerala and raised in Chennai. Anita always had an affinity towards writing and the courage to pursue it under all

the situations. In every novel, Anita Nair thought about the woman's search for freedom and realization. In Anita Nair's fictions, her characters have come out of their struggles and quest their identity. Her Novels explore the freedom of the man to fulfill herself basically as a human being, independent of her various traditional roles as a daughter, wife, mother and so on. This article deals with self-discovery as seen in the works of women writers. Here it must be remembered first that as a Indian Writing in English has placed an independent status in the realm of Indian literature. Fictionary writing in Indian English. Women writer occupies a major role in the contemporary writing in Indian English. Women writers come away from traditional portraits of enduringly-sacrificing women toward conflicted female characters searching for identity and defined their victus. Anita Nair is one of the finest writers in writing in English.

It is pertinent to note that Valsala in "*The Man*" is the wife of Prabhakaran, an aged scholar. Valsala is not satisfied with him. So, she falls in love with Sridharan. She doesn't bother about the propriety. She realizes her inner mind and becomes the mistress of him. This incident shows the femininity of Valsala in the form of morality. As a matter of fact she is aware of the fact that every woman needs an energizer of love, freedom, equality and sex. She forth the new issues of woman's sexuality and She justifies herself as, "I am just forty years old. I want to be pushed into old age before its time. I want to live. I want passion. I want to know ecstasy. I want to tell myself, night after night" (Nair 130). Valsala emerges as a "New Woman". She breaks the traditional Indian society. So, she is usually satisfied with her affair with her neighbor Sridharan and does not feel guilty of it. Valsala achieves an identity in life but against the traditional manner. Valsala resorts to freedom not only psychologically but sexually too. When she resolves her inner conflicts, she is able to conquer self-identity. The second character Anjana, in the novel "*The Man*" was grown up in a beautiful atmosphere. She married to Ravindran, at the age of twenty. She has lost all her independence in the name of marriage. Her married life is not good. Whenever Anjana is ready for conversation, Ravindran feels irritated and leaves the place. She longs for love and freedom but it ends in failure. So, she develops to hate things including herself. Notably, one day Anjana goes to her parent's home in order to look after her mother. This gap becomes an escape from her traditional life. Ravindran's business failed and he decided